

Impact of Technology and Financial Innovation on Systemic Risk of Commercial Banks in Vietnam

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Abstract

Background: Vietnam's commercial banking sector is undergoing a profound transformation due to globalisation, digital innovation, and macroeconomic volatility. These shifts have heightened concerns over systemic risk, particularly in emerging markets where regulatory frameworks and internal governance structures are evolving.

Objective: This study examines the determinants of systemic risk in Vietnamese commercial banks, specifically isolating and assessing the differential impact of the macroeconomic environment, financial integration, regulatory factors, and internal bank characteristics, with a primary focus on the mediating roles of technology and financial innovation.

Methodology: The authors employed structural equation modelling on data from 450 bank managers across six major cities, assessing the direct and indirect effects of five key factors on systemic risk. Confirmatory factor analysis and Bootstrap techniques were applied to ensure model robustness.

Result: Technology and financial innovation have a positive impact on systemic risk, while legal frameworks and supervisory authorities significantly mitigate it. Internal governance, globalisation, and macroeconomic conditions also contribute, albeit to a lesser extent.

Conclusion: Robust regulatory oversight and governance structures are crucial for mitigating the risks associated with digital transformation. Internal banking capabilities and macroeconomic stability provide foundational support but are secondary to external regulatory and technological drivers.

Unique Contribution: This study offers a novel integration of technological innovation, governance, and macro-financial factors into a unified systemic risk model. It offers novel empirical insights for emerging economies, informing regulatory design by balancing digital transformation with financial stability in under-researched, rapidly evolving financial systems.

Key Recommendation: Policymakers and SME managers should strategically prioritise resource allocation and development strategies aimed at improving the workforce.

Keywords: Systemic risk, financial innovation, regulatory framework, digital transformation.

Introduction

In the context of the rapid development of the 4.0 Industrial Revolution, digital transformation has become an inevitable trend in the banking industry, enabling the optimisation of operations and enhancement of risk management (Neitzert & Petras, 2022). By applying digital technologies, such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data, blockchain, and cloud computing, banks can more effectively monitor, detect, and manage financial risks. Moreover, applying digital technology helps enhance the ability to manage credit, liquidity, and operational risks. However, technology helps improve risk management performance, and the level of investment and corporate governance capacity play an essential role in exploiting the benefits of digital transformation (Lamothe et al., 2024).

Moreover, global capital flows, economic shocks, and fast financial innovation have all made Vietnam's banking industry more vulnerable in recent years. Cyber risks and technology-induced liquidity mismatches are two examples of the additional layers of complexity and susceptibility introduced by digital transformation, which offer possibilities for increased efficiency and inclusivity (Wang & Yang, 2024). Concerns about the stability of the financial system are exacerbated by macroeconomic factors like interest rate fluctuations, currency risks, and fluctuating inflation. Despite the growing body of literature on systemic risk in industrialised economies, there is a noticeable lack of empirical studies that delve into developing economies like Vietnam and how they handle systemic vulnerabilities. Moreover, the effects of technology developments and digital finance are under-researched in the existing literature on systemic risk, which primarily examines traditional macroeconomic or institutional factors. Awwad et al. (2024) and Lamothe et al. (2024) note that the literature lacks a comprehensive framework that combines the internal governance structures of banks with the external policy environments.

The importance of systemic risk to the stability of the financial system has increased in light of recent global economic crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical conflicts, and rapid technological advancements. According to Cheng and He (2023), scholars have thoroughly examined the impact of macroeconomic variables, financial integration, and globalisation on systemic risk. Much remains unknown regarding the relationship between traditional systemic risk factors and technological and financial innovations in developing economies, such as Vietnam, particularly in this era of digital transformation. Past studies have largely overlooked the fact that regulatory frameworks and internal governance frameworks complement one another in mitigating systemic vulnerabilities.

Based on systemic risk and gap-filling, this study evaluates the technical and financial innovations, as well as the macroeconomic and institutional drivers, of Vietnam's commercial banking sector. Influence-chain banks should avoid shock-related losses without official assurances. To prevent deposit runs and losses, banks must increase interest rates on high-risk assets, monitor their counterparties, and strengthen bilateral relationships. Therefore, the objective of this study is to explore the impact of the macroeconomic environment, globalisation, financial integration, legal framework, supervisory authorities, technology, financial innovation, and internal factors of commercial banks on systemic risk, particularly the impact of technology and financial innovation on systemic risk in Vietnamese commercial banks.

Literature Review

Systemic risk (SR)

The relationship between agency theory and systemic risk in the banking industry highlights the conflicts of interest among shareholders, managers, and regulators. Asymmetric information, unbalanced incentives, and a lack of transparency can worsen the systemic vulnerabilities of commercial banks, as detailed in agency theory. Managers who prioritise short-term gains over long-term stability run the risk of taking excessive risks, which can harm shareholders and the economy (Lamothe et al., 2024), as stated in the article. The organisation now faces new challenges brought forth by digitisation and globalisation. Managerial accountability and regulatory oversight are under scrutiny due to concerns raised by the increased complexity of operations and the prevalence of cybersecurity breaches resulting from technological advancements. The growth of cross-border financial operations brought about by globalisation is making it increasingly difficult for multinational stakeholders to align their interests, as noted by Awwad et al. (2024). This research explores the impact of internal governance, technological advancements, regulatory frameworks, and globalisation on systemic risk, grounded in agency theory. Using agency theory in conjunction with new financing and technological developments, this study examines the challenges faced by developing countries in their efforts to undergo digital transformation. The failure of just one entity could cause the collapse of an economic system or market. Markets and financial institutions are highly interdependent, which fosters this interconnection. A crucial component of systemic banking risk is the possibility of a crisis-inspiring bank failure.

Theoretical Framework

Macroeconomic environment (ME)

Roaring bad loan ratios, declining liquidity, recessions, and tightening monetary policy affect banks. Macroeconomic factors, as well as technical and financial developments, affect banking system risk, according to Zhou et al. (2023). Macroeconomic conditions influence asset quality and liquidity, while technological innovation complicates risk management and operational processes (Wang & Yang, 2024). The stability of the financial system impacts macroeconomic factors, including inflation, interest rates, GDP growth, and exchange rates. Volatility impacts liquidity, interbank confidence, and credit quality, thereby increasing the likelihood of systemic disruptions (Markose et al., 2023; Ahmad, 2023). Creating strong regulatory frameworks, investing in secure technology, and managing risk are essential to reducing banking system risk. Hypotheses H1 and H2 were proposed in Figure 1.

Globalisation and financial integration (GI)

Globalisation and financial integration make banks more vulnerable to external shocks. Each bank and country will have its pros and cons, depending on the level of integration and management. Globalisation and financial integration are connecting multinational banks. This makes enormous sums of money readily available, increasing the likelihood of a systemic crisis affecting several institutions (Anwar et al., 2023; Wang & Yang, 2024). Research on globalisation is mixed. According to some studies, diversity in financial markets can make them more stable; however, interdependencies and spillovers across borders can also make them more fragile. In Figure 1, the authors offered hypotheses H3 and H4.

Legal framework and supervisory authorities (LS)

The regulatory environment and supervisory bodies help reduce banking system risks. However, rules and oversight must be tailored to each country's specific circumstances to strike a balance between systemic stability and economic growth. Enhanced international coordination is necessary to safeguard the banking system against the risks of financial integration and globalisation. Lastly, regulatory authorities and a robust legal framework must address the challenges posed by technological and financial innovations to mitigate risks to the banking system (Gao et al., 2023; Cheng & He, 2023). There is a lack of consistency in determining the efficacy of regulations in contexts where technology shocks and globalisation are causing rapid changes, although robust regulatory regimes are typically associated with reduced systemic risk (Basdekis et al., 2022). Therefore, the authors proposed hypotheses H5 and H6 in Figure 1.

Technology and financial innovation (TI)

Technological advancements are causing a significant shift in the financial sector, bringing both opportunities and challenges. In the context of global digitisation, the key to the financial industry's sustainable development lies in combining technology's potential with the establishment of an acceptable regulatory framework. To strike a balance between innovation and systemic stability, financial institutions and regulators alike will need to adapt swiftly (Neitzert & Petras, 2022). Technological transformation not only increases operational efficiency and customer experience but also brings challenges in risk management and financial stability (Li, 2023; Rjoub et al., 2023). To minimise adverse impacts, banks need to develop appropriate internal risk management strategies and coordinate with regulatory agencies to create a practical legal framework for systemic risk management in the context of technological innovation. Therefore, the authors proposed hypotheses H7 and H8 in Figure 1.

Internal factors of commercial banks (IF)

Inadequate transparency, charter capital, or liquidity can lead to a decline in confidence and a domino effect (Lamothe et al., 2024; Kunz & Heitz, 2021). Understanding how banks function inside is critical for avoiding systemic risks and stabilising the economy. Risk might propagate across banks through the interbank market and related financial channels if these factors are not adequately controlled. To mitigate the negative impact of internal factors on banking system risks, investing in technology, promoting a transparent corporate culture, and enhancing internal governance are necessary (Neitzert & Petras, 2022). Therefore, the authors proposed hypothesis H9 in Figure 1.

This SEM model illustrates how the macroeconomic environment, globalisation and financial integration, legal framework and supervisory authorities, technology and financial innovation, and internal factors of commercial banks affect systemic risk, as shown in Figure 1.

Source: The authors proposed the model

Figure 1: A research model for critical factors influencing the systemic risk of commercial banks

Figure 1 suggests that the study model analyses the effects of the macroeconomic environment, globalisation and financial integration, regulatory framework and supervisory authorities, technology and financial innovation, and bank internal factors on banking system risks. The research quantifies the impact of each factor on systemic risk and recommends policies to mitigate the risk to the banking sector. This model measures commercial bank systemic risk using an equation structural model (SEM) and the five independent variables above.

Research Methods

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining qualitative expert interviews with quantitative survey analysis. It employs Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to examine the relationships between five key factors that influence systemic risk in Vietnamese commercial banks. A standardised questionnaire was used to collect data from 450 bank managers spread throughout six major cities.

Qualitative Method: Fifteen risk management specialists from big Vietnamese commercial banks participated in in-depth interviews for the qualitative study. The experts were chosen for their extensive knowledge, practical expertise, capacity to formulate effective policies, and academic credentials (Director of the branch). The primary goals of the interviews were to determine what variables impact systemic risk, to validate the initial scale, and to tailor the questionnaire to the real-world situation in Vietnam.

Quantitative Method – 3 steps: (1) Survey design: A questionnaire was developed based on the theoretical model, utilising a 5-level Likert scale. The survey was distributed to 450 bank

managers in 6 major cities. (2) Data analysis: Data processing using SPSS and AMOS, reliability testing (Cronbach's Alpha), convergent validity (EFA, CFA), and SEM structural model analysis. (3) Model validation: Evaluate model fit (GFI, CFI, TLI, RMSEA), test hypotheses, and analyse 50.000 bootstrap samples to ensure the stability and reliability of the results (Hair et al., 2018).

(1) Survey design: Based on sound scientific and statistical reasoning, a sample size of 450 is ideal and does not require more investigation. According to statistical theory, a sample size of 200 to 400 is sufficient for evaluating structural equation modelling (SEM). However, a sample of 450 meets and even exceeds this baseline need, leading to improved reliability. In addition, the recommended sample size is 10–20 times the number of variables, based on the rule for sample size related to the number of variables observed. A sample size of 450 is within the optimal range of 300–600 for around 20–30 observed variables. Assuming suitable and diverse respondents are surveyed for the 450 polls, the sample ensures a high level of representativeness.

(2) Data analysis: The study employs a structural equation model (SEM) using Amos software to test the hypotheses, ensuring a robust analysis of the complex relationships among latent variables. Moreover, the model specification: (1) the dependent variable is the systemic risk (SR); (2) the independent variables are ME, GI, LS, TI, and IF. (3) Model validation: (i) Cronbach's Alpha ensures internal consistency of survey items. (ii) Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) validates the dimensionality of constructs. (iii) Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) assesses model fit and convergent validity. (iv) Model fit indices: Goodness of Fit Index (GFI ≥ 0.90), Comparative Fit Index (CFI ≥ 0.90), Root Mean Square Error of Approximation (RMSEA ≤ 0.08); (v) Hypothesis testing based on path coefficients from SEM are used to evaluate the relationships between independent variables and systemic risk. (vi) The robustness of the estimations is tested using bootstrap analysis with 50.000 samples. The study employs structural equation modelling (SEM) to investigate the factors that influence systemic vulnerabilities in the Vietnamese banking industry. It captures the direct and indirect effects of the independent variables on systemic risk (Hair et al., 2018).

(3) Model validation: Model fit indicators (CFI, GFI, TLI, and RMSEA) are available in SEM and allow for a comprehensive evaluation of the model's agreement with empirical data; this is something that ordinary linear regression does not achieve. In addition, SEM can clarify direct, indirect, or mediated effects. Borrowing costs and liquidity issues are two examples of how monetary policy can influence systemic risk. By combining qualitative and quantitative aspects, SEM can manage complex, multidimensional data and mitigate the effects of multicollinearity, a common problem in studies of economic variables. Finally, SEM enables the testing and verification of theoretical models with empirical data, yielding analytical results that are both precise and practically useful. From a technical and substantive standpoint, thanks to these benefits, SEM excels in helping to develop strategies to address systemic banking challenges.

Study Results

Testing critical factors affecting systemic risk at commercial banks in Vietnam

The results of the reliability tests were conducted on the scales measuring factors that impact systemic risk using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient. The observed variables were highly reliable and internally consistent, as all scales had an alpha value > 0.8. Specifically, the "Globalization and financial integration" scale had the highest dependability (0.950), suggesting that the examined factors were consistently and steadily evaluated. The average factor scores showed a generally high degree of agreement among respondents, ranging from 2.426 to 3.405. It is worth mentioning that systemic risk received the lowest average score (2.426), indicating that there is now a minimal level of concern, but that it still requires control. The dependability of the scales is shown in Table 1, which provides a solid foundation for the forthcoming investigations in the SEM model.

Table 1: Testing SEM model for factors affecting systemic risk at commercial banks in Vietnam

Relationships	Standardized Estimate	Estimate	S.E	C.R	P	Hypothesis	Result
ME → TI	0.117	0.085	0.030	2.789	0.005	H2	Accepted
GI → TI	0.124	0.145	0.047	3.071	0.002	H4	Accepted
LS → TI	0.463	0.367	0.041	8.960	***	H5	Accepted
TI → IF	0.167	0.175	0.054	3.235	0.001	H8	Accepted
TI → SR	0.326	0.192	0.032	5.925	***	H7	Accepted
LS → SR	0.250	0.117	0.024	4.851	***	H6	Accepted
GI → SR	0.133	0.092	0.028	3.319	***	H3	Accepted
ME → SR	0.121	0.052	0.022	2.349	0.019	H1	Accepted
IF → SR	0.235	0.133	0.026	5.044	***	H9	Accepted

Source: processed from SPSS 20.0, Amos, Note *** significance at 0.01.

Table 1 presents the outcomes of the SEM model testing, illustrating the link between the components and systemic risk in Vietnam's commercial banks. The proposed model is confirmed to be suitable as all nine hypotheses are accepted with high statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). It is worth mentioning that the most significant effect on systemic risk is "Technological and financial innovation" (TI), with a beta coefficient of 0.326. This highlights that technology serves a dual purpose: it can enhance efficiency while also introducing new hazards. The significance of macro-governance is underlined by the fact that the component "Legal framework and supervisory agencies" (LS) also has a substantial impact ($\beta = 0.250$). The study model's causal links are supported by statistically significant standardised correlation coefficients surpassing the 0.1 level.

Source: processed from SPSS 20.0, Amos

Figure 2: Testing SEM for factors affecting systemic risk at commercial banks in Vietnam

Figure 2 depicts the paths of influence between the five key components and systemic risk (SR) at commercial banks in Vietnam. The model fits the empirical data well, as shown by the fit indices within acceptable limits: GFI = 0.872, TLI = 0.911, CFI = 0.926, and RMSEA = 0.078. With impact values of 0.44 and 0.25, respectively, the two elements that have the most significant influence on systemic risk are "Technological and financial innovation" (TI) and "Legal and supervisory framework" (LS). "Globalisation," "Macro environment," and "Internal bank factors" are three other elements that significantly affect the situation, either directly or indirectly. This demonstrates that the current systemic risk structure is complex and spans multiple sectors.

Table 2: Testing average variance extracted for factors affecting systemic risk

Code	CR	AVE	MSV	Results
GI	0.830	0.560	0.034	Good
LS	0.934	0.781	0.305	Good
ME	0.928	0.763	0.051	Good
IF	0.911	0.720	0.104	Good
SR	0.880	0.649	0.272	Good
TI	0.876	0.705	0.305	Good

Source: Authors' own work

Table 2 presents the findings of the convergent and discriminant validity tests, as measured by Cronbach's alpha (CR), Average Variance Extracted (AVE), and Mean Squared Variance (MSV) indices. The scale's convergent validity and composite reliability were determined to be satisfactory because all latent variables attained CR > 0.8 and AVE > 0.5. For instance, the latent construct was well-measured by the variables "Legal and supervisory framework" (LS)

with an average variance extracted (AVE) of 0.781 and by "Macro environment" (ME) with an AVE of 0.763. All components having AVE values higher than MSV further confirmed the discriminant validity between the model's variables. The results laid a solid foundation for the following SEM analysis, demonstrating that the measurement structure was stable and could clearly differentiate theoretical notions. Table 2 indicates that all nine hypotheses were approved. This test employed the Bootstrap method with 50,000 samples, using a significance level of 0.05 (C.R. < 1.96), to assess the variables affecting systemic risk at Vietnamese commercial banks.

Discussion of Findings

During the fast digital and financial transition, the study sheds light on the factors that pose a systemic risk to Vietnam's commercial banking sector. The dual function of digital transformation is emphasised by the fact that out of the five predictors, technology and financial innovation (TI) was the strongest driver of linked systemic risk ($\beta = 0.326$) (Kyoud et al., 2024; Li, 2023). While advancements such as digital payments, AI, and blockchain improve operational efficiency, they also introduce additional cybersecurity, operational failure, and interconnectivity-related concerns. This aligns with earlier research highlighting the systemic effects of FinTech growth in developing economies.

In addition, the systemic risk is significantly reduced ($\beta = 0.250$), and technological adoption is simultaneously promoted ($\beta = 0.463$) by the regulatory framework and supervisory agencies (LS), highlighting their essential role in maintaining a balance between innovation and stability (Goyal et al., 2023; Chen & Shen, 2024). This research lends credence to the idea that digital banking may be safely integrated with well-thought-out regulatory frameworks that reduce risks. The effects of globalisation and financial integration (GI) on systemic risk ($\beta = 0.133$) and innovation ($\beta = 0.124$) were mild, suggesting that unchecked cross-border links and capital flows can worsen vulnerabilities (Bilal et al., 2024; Kedarya et al., 2023).

There were small but noticeable impacts from the external macroeconomic climate and internal bank variables. The importance of internal governance and economic stability cannot be overstated, as external legal and technical factors increasingly define systemic risk. Institutional transformation, innovation governance, and macroprudential regulation are the key findings addressing the policy challenges. The study found that technological and financial innovations can improve efficiency, but they also have the potential to raise systemic risk. Nevertheless, the model implies that regulatory frameworks, macroeconomic dynamics, and globalisation drive the expansion of financial technology innovation.

Conclusions and Policy Recommendations

Conclusions

This study examines the systemic risk in Vietnam's commercial banking sector in light of the rapidly evolving digital and international financial landscape. This study employs Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) with a large sample of banking specialists to elucidate the intricate relationships between digital transformation, macroeconomic conditions, globalisation, regulatory frameworks, and internal bank governance. Results reveal that new financial innovations and technological advances greatly affect systemic risk directly and indirectly. These advances increase productivity and service quality but can introduce security and operational issues. Regulatory frameworks and supervisory bodies mitigate systemic risks by

promoting compliance, transparency, and the safe use of technology. The study also reveals that cross-border interdependencies and external shocks exacerbate systemic risk through financial integration and globalisation. A bank's governance and financial performance are less important but fundamental to its resiliency. Fundamental macroeconomic conditions have a moderate impact on systemic risk; therefore, stable economic policies are crucial. The report offers a comprehensive framework for understanding emerging market systemic risk and provides practical guidance for regulators and financial institutions.

Policy Recommendations

Based on the empirical findings, especially the significant impact of technological and financial innovation (TI), legal framework and supervisory authorities (LS), globalisation and financial integration (GI), internal factors of commercial banks (IF), and macroeconomic environment (ME) on systemic risk (SR), the following targeted policy measures are proposed:

(1) Improve technology and financial innovation (TI): Commercial banks, Fintech companies, and regulatory authorities should collaborate to improve innovation and systemic risk solutions. Managers can help banks implement global technology management best practices by sharing their expertise. Regulators, such as the State Bank of Vietnam, should establish a centralised regulatory sandbox to facilitate controlled experimentation of digital financial products, thereby enhancing supervisory oversight of financial innovation while mitigating cyber and operational risks. The regulator should run the sandbox to ensure accountability, data protection, and consumer safety, not banks. The banking system must invest in training and capacity building for bank employees to enhance their skills and expertise in digital banking, data analytics, risk management, and customer service. Develop human resources and professional development programs to have a skilled workforce capable of driving banking transformation initiatives.

(2) Improved legal framework and supervisory authorities (LS): The Vietnamese government should propose policy actions based on dynamic regulatory frameworks with periodically updated legislation to handle new concerns, including digital banking, Fintech adoption, and cybersecurity. Stress testing and capital adequacy standards should be strengthened for systemic risk assessment. Instead of compliance-focused supervision, risk-based supervision prioritises high-risk organisations and activities. Promote system-wide risk assessments to anticipate vulnerabilities. Standardised reporting formats can also be required to promote transparency and openness in financial operations and systemic risk assessment. Increased enforcement should assure regulatory compliance. Finally, digital banking systems must comply with cybersecurity laws to address data breaches, cyberattacks, and operational disruptions. In addition, the State needs to ensure the completion of a legal framework that fosters innovation, competition, and stability in financial and banking activities, with clear and transparent regulations to support digital banking transformation initiatives. This framework should also protect consumer rights and data privacy while managing systemic risks.

(3) Enhance globalisation and financial integration (GI): Financial integration fosters innovation through competition and modernisation, promoting economic growth and development. It increases systemic vulnerabilities due to cross-border linkages and global market shocks. Thus, commercial banks should establish capital flow monitoring techniques to manage foreign capital and mitigate global risks arising from fluctuations in the international market. Plan for global economic crisis hazards. Finally, it promotes domestic funding to reduce reliance on foreign capital and diversify. Encourage commercial banks to comply with international standards in digital banking, risk management, and compliance to mitigate

globalisation risks and diversify their revenue streams by expanding into less volatile markets or offering innovative products. Additionally, better data exchange and interagency coordination. Oversight gaps reduce systemic risk detection. One of the most significant impacts of these technologies is their ability to extend financial services to underserved populations, promoting financial inclusion and empowerment. By providing access to banking services via mobile devices, even in remote areas, individuals and businesses can participate more fully in the formal economy, leading to increased productivity, entrepreneurship, and economic development.

(4) Improved internal factors of commercial banks (IF): Financial reporting transparency and governance improvements are needed to link internal practices to systemic risk mitigation. Commercial bank governance should stress accountability, risk management, and strategic decision-making. Commercial banks educate managers on governance and systemic risk. Regulatory and stakeholder mandates for comprehensive financial disclosures led to a rise in financial transparency. International accounting standards establish consistency and comparability. Last but not least, technological procedure automation improves efficiency by eliminating human error and inefficiency. Banks can improve their operational performance by incentivising their employees to get training. Initiate programs to educate people on how to manage their finances more effectively and ensure they understand what to expect from banks when utilising their services. The fight against fraud and in favour of honest and open banking should be bolstered by enhancing consumer protection tools.

(5) Improved macroeconomic environment (ME): To lessen economic uncertainty, Vietnam stabilises interest rates and aims to lower inflation. Growth over the long run should be the goal of monetary policy. To protect its economy from geopolitical unpredictability and worldwide financial crises, Vietnam is bolstering its fiscal buffers. Enhance economic robustness by implementing systemic reforms. The promotion of innovation, rather than systemic danger, is the result of stable interest rates, strong GDP growth, and good management of inflation. Moreover, risk pathways should inform macroprudential instruments. Monetary policy tools, such as loan-to-value ratios and counter-cyclical capital buffers, need to be adjusted in response to inflation shocks and credit booms, particularly when the former is caused by external volatility.

Limitations and future research: Several limitations should be considered in this investigation. First, cross-sectional data make it challenging to track systemic risk or adjust to macro-financial conditions. Future research should use longitudinal or panel data to capture dynamic interactions. Second, the analysis only covers Vietnam, which may limit its applicability to other rising markets. Comparative regional studies could improve context. Third, the SEM model captures complex interactions but may not address endogeneity in the financial system or latent confounding variables. Future research should incorporate real-time risk indicators, such as digital transaction volumes, cyber risk incidents, and market sentiment indexes, to enhance predictive capabilities. Regulators, FinTech firms, and consumers could be added to stakeholder views better to understand the structural risks of the digital financial ecosystem.

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